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Exploring Coaching Styles of Cooperating Teachers

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Abstract

This study focused on examining the various coaching styles employed by the selected five (5) cooperating teachers towards pre-service teachers in Holy Trinity College of General Santos City, specifically the elementary department. Coaching styles were the different approaches and methods that the cooperating teacher used to support and guide pre-service teachers during their practicum or pre-service teaching. Thematic Analysis was utilized as the methodology to identify and analyze major themes derived from the collected data. This involved a detailed examination of the coaching styles and methods used by cooperating teachers to support and guide pre-service teachers in their professional development. The findings show that the primary coaching style employed by cooperating teachers is instructional coaching, as reported by the majority of participants. Additionally, several participants mentioned the use of democratic coaching and vision coaching. These results underscore the diverse coaching styles utilized by cooperating teachers. Moreover, this study also highlights the impact of coaching styles utilized by cooperating teachers on pre-service teachers. Becomes open-minded under instructional coaching was cited by the participants as the most observed impact of coaching styles. This is followed by becomes independent in teaching under the democratic coaching style. Next is, becomes realistic which is under vision coaching. And lastly, becomes confident in teaching, which is also under the democratic coaching style. We recommend using both surveys and interviews to understand how these styles affect the learning and development of pre-service teachers.

Keywords: *coaching styles, cooperating teachers, democratic coaching, instructional coaching, pre-service teacher*

Introduction

In education, coaching styles play a crucial role in shaping the teaching experiences of pre-service teachers. As a future pre-service teacher, we find that coaching styles are more than just methods, they are approaches that can deeply impact our practice teaching journey. When a cooperating teacher adopts a coaching style, it creates a space for open communication and mutual respect. There are a variety of coaching styles to support us, future pre-service teachers, as we take our initial steps into the teaching profession. Coaching styles not only enhance our teaching abilities but also shape our leadership qualities. As we experience different coaching styles, we may discover our strengths and areas for improvement, ultimately influencing how we guide and inspire others in the future. Each coaching style offers unique benefits and challenges, all of which are important in helping us become great teachers.

As an education student, one of the most exciting parts of our college life is becoming a pre-service teacher because it provides us the opportunity to apply our knowledge, build relationships, develop professionally, make a difference, and grow personally. It is a crucial step for us in becoming a skilled and effective educator. A pre-service teacher is a student enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Secondary Education, or another relevant teacher education program. We believe that receiving guidance from experienced classroom experts is indispensable for becoming an effective teacher.

Cooperating teacher, who plays a pivotal role in our development, offers us not just direction, but also valuable advice and unwavering support. Through their mentorship, we may be able to enhance our teaching skills, gain confidence, and navigate the complexities of classroom management and instructional strategies. This personalized guidance provided by cooperating teachers plays a pivotal role in shaping us into competent and impactful educators. It goes beyond just teaching methods; it involves understanding our unique strengths, weaknesses, learning styles, and aspirations.

Our study involved conducting interviews with cooperating teachers from the Elementary Department of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City. The aim was to understand the various coaching styles employed by cooperating teachers while guiding pre-service teachers during their practical teaching experiences.

Research Questions

This study aimed to know the different coaching styles employed by cooperating teachers in coaching pre-service teachers. The following specific problems that need to be resolved are the following:

1. What are the different coaching styles employed by the selected cooperating teachers at Holy Trinity College of General Santos City?
2. How do these coaching styles impact the learning experience of pre-service teachers?

Literature Review

Coaching Styles of Cooperating Teachers

Coaching styles of cooperating teachers refer to the different approaches and methods they use to support and guide student teachers during their practicum or student teaching experience. Democratic coaching style is a type of coaching where individuals are in control of their own learning. They make their own choices, and it enhances their skills by encouraging them to share their input on decisions and thoughts (Berzman, 2023). Vision coaching aims to empower employees by providing them with clear guidance and a comprehensive strategy for reaching their goals. Cooperating teachers and pre-service teachers work together in teacher education programs, focusing on hands-on learning in teaching (Berzman, 2023; Hoffman, 2015). Instructional coaching focuses on enhancing the teaching methods of the teachers and improving student learning results. The coach provides personalized support, feedback, and resources to help the pre-service teacher refine their instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, and content knowledge. (Gibbons & Cobb, 2017).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive qualitative research design, which involved gathering and analyzing information that is not in number form, aiming to understand ideas, viewpoints, or experiences. It helped gain a deep understanding of a problem or generate fresh ideas for further research (Bhandari, 2023). This study only focused on descriptive qualitative, which aimed to explore the coaching styles of cooperating teachers in order to comprehend their behavior and motivations from their own point of view. Moreover, this study highlighted the coaching styles of the elementary cooperating teachers in Holy Trinity College of General Santos City, Elementary Department.

Participants

The participants of this study were the elementary cooperating teachers at Holy Trinity College in General Santos City in the school year 2022-2023. In this study, five (5) cooperating teachers were chosen as participants. The confirmed cooperating teachers were invited to participate, ensuring that a particular subset of individuals was included in the study.

Instruments

In this study, we utilized an interview guide as a data-gathering tool to collect data. We strictly safeguard the information that we collected from them and in addition, we conducted a thorough examination of it, as we analyzed and interpreted it for our study entitled exploring coaching styles of cooperating teachers. We asked questions about the different coaching styles employed by the cooperating teachers and the impact of it to the pre-service teachers. We exercised carefulness by employing open-ended questions.

Procedure

Before conducting the interviews, we prepared a letter to conduct a study, which was subsequently sent to the principal of the Elementary Department. Then after the approval of the letter, we went to the Academic Coordinator to assist us for the possible qualified participants. He assigned five (5) cooperating teachers who may participate in our study.

During the interviews, we used our mobile phones to record what the participants had to say, and ensure not to reveal their identities. Throughout the interview process, we encountered challenges, as it coincided with our intramurals day, resulting in scheduling difficulties for our participants. Hence, the interview process extended over several days.

After the interview, we started transcribing. We listened to the recordings and looked at what the participants answered. We also read through what they said to understand how their experiences affected the way they guide pre-service teachers.

Data Analysis

We employed thematic analysis as a qualitative data analysis technique in this study. It is a method for examining qualitative data. Thematic analysis helps us find and understand the main themes or meaning within the information we collected from the participants (Clarke & Braun, 2018).

To conduct the analysis, we manually transcribed the audio recordings of the interviews. We carefully reviewed the contents of the interviews, identified key themes and patterns in the responses of the participants, highlighted essential information, and marked similar statements made by the participants for each research question relevant to the findings of the study. The contents of the interviews were thoroughly analyzed and evaluated by the researchers to uncover meaningful insights and draw conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers made certain that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College to avoid engaging in practices that may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those with whom he/she sought to conduct research with. The ethical standards were the following: informed consent, data privacy, gender sensitivity and cultural sensitivity.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the data on the coaching styles employed by cooperating teachers towards pre-service teachers. This section also included the impact of these styles on the learning experience of the pre-service teachers and the general themes and core ideas drawn from these analyses.

Profile of Cooperating Teachers

The primary focus of this study was to determine the coaching styles employed by the cooperating teachers towards pre-service teachers. We selected five (5) cooperating teachers from Holy Trinity College of General Santos City in the Elementary department. Our selection criteria included factors such; they must have an experience in coaching pre-service teachers. They must have at least two (2) to three (3) years of experience as a cooperating teacher, and they must have been a cooperating teacher in the Holy Trinity College Elementary Department in SY 2022-2023 and 2023-2024, second semester. To safeguard the privacy of these participants, we opted to assign codes, using CT (Cooperating Teacher) and a number, such as CT1, to facilitate identification during the research process.

CT1 is a 24-year-old female. She has 2 years of experience as a cooperating teacher. She believed that integrating democratic coaching and vision coaching is effective because it helps pre-service teachers perform well.

CT2 is a 24-year-old female. She has worked as a cooperating teacher for 2 years. She provides feedback to pre-service teachers to help them improve their teaching performance by addressing their weaknesses.

CT3 is a 25-year-old female. She has accumulated 2 years of experience in the role of a cooperating teacher. She believed that pre-service teachers should experience a real-world classroom setting instead of relying solely on ideal concepts.

CT4 is a 29-year-old female. She has 2 years of experience working as a cooperating teacher. She believed that coaching styles have a significant impact on pre-service teachers, enhancing their performance and helping them acquire knowledge in handling learners.

CT5 is a 24-year-old male. He has worked as a cooperating teacher for 2 years. He believed that incorporating democratic coaching and instructional coaching styles can reduce the pressure on practice teachers, as it allows them the freedom to implement their own strategies.

The findings of the study are presented in Tables generated from the thematic analysis.

Table 1. *Coaching Styles Employed by Cooperating Teachers at Holy Trinity College of General Santos City*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Democratic Coaching	Free to implement strategies to use such as games Encourage creativity
Vision Coaching	Help teachers during activity sessions
Instructional Coaching	Advice is provided in teaching performance/ methods

Table 2. *Themes, Core Ideas, and Frequency of Responses of the Impact of Coaching Styles to the Learning Experience of Pre-service Teachers*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>
Becomes Independent in Teaching	They can teach without the supervision of cooperating teachers.	Typical
	They are becoming creative and having the initiative on what to do.	Typical
Becomes Confident in Teaching	They get better every time they teach	Variant
	They can now showcase different strategies and skills.	Typical
Becomes Realistic	They realized that theory is different from reality.	Typical
	They acquired strategies on classroom management.	Variant
Becomes Open-minded	They can now take advice as lessons rather than criticisms.	General

Frequency of Responses were interpreted as general, typical and variant. General if most of the participants had the same answers to the given questions. Typical if only a few had the same response and variant – if they had dissimilar responses.

Conclusions

Our study explored different coaching styles employed by cooperating teachers who mentor future teachers, revealing a great opportunity for improvement. We found that democratic, vision, and instructional coaching help these new teachers develop their skills and become confident, effective educators. This research deepens our understanding of how mentor teachers support their students and offers valuable lessons and a clear guide for anyone interested in this area. It shows how changing the way feedback is viewed, from criticism to valuable advice, can greatly benefit new teachers, helping them work more independently and confidently.

In particular, vision coaching, which involves real-life teaching scenarios, prepares these new teachers well for their careers by emphasizing practical experience. Democratic coaching also stands out because it boosts teachers' confidence and encourages them to make their own decisions in teaching, leading to better results. These coaching methods do more than teach; they transform how teachers approach their work, leading to better teaching overall. This study not only adds to our academic discussions but also suggests practical ways to improve teaching through better coaching, helping make every teaching moment more effective. Truly, coaching styles really play a key role in enhancing and developing the teaching experience of pre-service teachers.

References

- Aabi, Mustapha (2022). Pedagogical: Issues in Teaching Practice. Morocco. Souss Impression Édition - Agadir. p. 43.
- Akasha, O. (2020). "Frozen Up Like an Ice Cube!": The Influence of Situated Learning on Pre-Service Teachers' Cultural and Linguistic Awareness. *The Qualitative Report*, 25(9), 3391-3424.
- Amorim, C. and Ribeiro S. (2024). Cooperating Teachers' Perceptions and Contributions to Preservice Teachers' Professional Identities. *Education Sciences*, 14.
- Berzman, R. (2023). 11 Coaching Styles To Consider (Plus Why They're Important). *Indeed*.
- Bhandari, P. (2023). What Is Qualitative Research? | Methods & Examples. *Scribbr*.
- Bhebhe, S. (2022). Mentoring pre-service teachers in situated learning: a case study of a Zimbabwean teacher training college. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 14(2), 550-558.
- Block, H. (2019). *The Influence of Instructional Coaching on Teacher Efficacy and Student Achievement*. Clear Lake. The University of Houston.
- Can, D. (2019). Pre-service efl teachers' reflections: the contribution of teaching practicum on academic success and self-improvement. *People International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(3), 963-984.
- Ciampa, K., & Gallagher, T. (2019). Blogging to Enhance In-Service Teachers' Professional Learning and Development during Collaborative Inquiry. *Journal Articles; Reports – Research*.
- Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2018). Thematic Analysis. In: Michalos, A.C. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Creswell, J. & Poth, C. (2018). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*. SAGE publications.
- DepEd Order No. 3. s. 2007. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2007/01/DO_s2007_003.pdf
- Gabasa (2023). Subject coordinators, head teachers and master teachers coaching practices and its impact on teachers' instructional performance in Nagcarlan District Laguna: Basis for enhanced teacher development program. *Consortia Academia*. 2023 IJRSE – Volume 12 Issue 1.
- Göker, M. Ü. (2021). Reflective coaching: training for development of instructional skills and sense of efficacy of pre-service efl teachers. *Dil Ve Dilbilimi Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 17(1), 423-447.
- Gonzalvo, B., Laksamana, G., and Sapungan, R. (2018). Mentoring Practices of English Cooperating Teachers in Public Secondary Schools. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*. Vol. 6 No.3
- Hammond, L. & Moore, W. M. (2018). Teachers taking up explicit instruction: the impact of a professional development and directive instructional coaching model. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(7), 110-133.
- Hope, S., Abrams, L., & Marshall, D. T. (2022). Coaching in teacher residency programs: a strategy for professional learning and development for in-service teachers. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, 11(4), 434-451.
- Hoque KE, Raya ZT. (2023). Relationship between Principals' Leadership Styles and Teachers' Behavior. *Behavioral Sciences*. 2023; 13(2):111.
- Jaafari, F. (2019). A theoretical understanding of transformational leadership. *International Journal of Development Research* Volume: 09
- Jones et al., (2019). The Effects of Coachee Personality and Goal Orientation on Performance Improvement Following Coaching: A Controlled Field Experiment. *Applied Psychology*.
- Kilic, D. & Saglam, N., (2023). Science Insights Education Frontiers, v19 n2 p3057-3071. *Journal Articles; Reports – Research*
- Kim, S., Park, S., Love, A., & Pang, T. C. (2021). Coaching style, sport enjoyment, and intent to continue participation among artistic swimmers. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 16(3), 477-489.

Mahmud, H., Raupu, S., Maharani, D. and Alauddin, A. (2021). Democratic leadership and its impact on teacher performance. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(3), 1556-1570.

Maravé-Vivas, M., Salvador-García, C., Gil-Gómez, J., Valverde-Esteve, T., and Martín-Moya, R. (2022). How can service-learning shape the political perspectives of pre-service teachers? a program in the field of physical education. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(15), 9175.

Matsko, K., Ronfeldt, M., Nolan, H., Klugman, J., Reiningger, M., and Brockman, S. (2020). Cooperating Teacher as Model and Coach: What Leads to Student Teachers' Perceptions of Preparedness. *Journal of Teacher Education* 2020, Vol. 71(1) 41–62

Silva, A. (2023). The impact of technological advancements on HR practices and leadership in Brazil. *Journal of Human Resource and Leadership*, 8(1), page 49.

Songsingchai, S. (2021). The study of the effectiveness of coaching program for pre- service teachers to communicative listening-speaking skills. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 12(2), 21.

Tican, C. (2019). Pre-service primary school and pre-school teachers' perception of individual entrepreneurship and opinions about their creative thinking tendency. *International*.

Tope, M. (2023) A Multiple Case Study: The Impact of Instructional Coaching on Novice Teachers. *acu.edu*.

Tsarkos, A. (2024). *Coaching and Educational Leadership Development: Harnessing Coaching for Leadership Excellence*. United States of America. IGI Global Publishing

Uluçınar, U. & Aypay, A. (2018). An evaluation of the relationship between pre-service teachers' critical thinking dispositions and democratic values in terms of critical pedagogy. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 7(3), 1.

Urquhart, D., Bloom, G. & Loughead, T. (2020). The Development, Articulation, and Implementation of a Coaching Vision of Multiple Championship-Winning University Ice Hockey Coaches. *International Sport Coaching Journal*. Volume 7: Issue 3

Yüksel, İ. & Başaran, B. (2019). The change in elt pre-service teachers' cognition during teaching practicum. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 7(10), 58.

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